

Professional Nurses' Awareness and Practice of Patient-Centered Care Approach to Nursing Care at Jericho Specialist Hospital, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated professional nurses' awareness and practice of Patient-Centered Care Approach to nursing care at Jericho Specialist Hospital, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was adopted using questionnaires to elicit response from respondents. The study population was all professional nurses working presently in the hospital. Purposive sampling was employed in the study. Total enumeration was used in the study meaning all nurses who were on duty as at the time of data collection were included in the study. A structured questionnaire was used to explore their opinions as regard the nurses' awareness and practice of Patient Centered Care. The instrument for data collection was subjected to face and content validity technique. The questionnaire was given to an expert in nursing management and practice and statistical analyst for critiquing, suggestions and amendments. The instrument was administered to the respondents on the day approved by the selected hospital authority for the exercise. The data collected from the study was analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study revealed that the awareness of nurses on Patient Centred Care was good which means nurses were very much aware of Patient Centred Care approach, while practice was below average, which showed that nurses' awareness of Patient Centred Care does influence their practice of Patient Centred Care. It was recommended that nurse administrator should ensure utilization of Patient Centred Care approach in their facility

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for effective, efficient and quality healthcare delivery so as to improve patients' health outcome and thereby produce nurses' satisfaction.

Keywords: Awareness, Practice, Patient-Centered Care Approach, Nursing Care,

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Introduction:

Nursing is the corner stone and bed rock of health care professions where others are built. It is a call to serve humanity, while medicine focused on the sickness, nursing focuses on the sick (patient). For these patients to have an adequate and a satisfactory nursing care they must be involved in their care plan. Their contributions to their healthcare should not be underestimated as they are at the centre of the problem and at the receiving end, so they know where the problem is, how it started, and how well they can be assisted. Patient Centred Care can be traced to era of Florence Nightingale who said nursing should concentrate on the sick rather than the sickness. Nursing is now in the era of Evidenced Based Practice and to practice it successfully Patient Centred Care must be utilized. Patient Centred Care (PCC) should be an integral part of nursing care profession, to make them discharge their duties optimally, thus help patient to recuperate well, reducing their hospital's stay, cost of treatment, and separation from their loved ones.

Patient Centred Care (PCC) is the interaction between the clinician and the patient, and the clinician's ability to use the patient's knowledge and experiences to guide the nursing care. Being patient centered means health care providers is taking into account the patient's desire for information and for sharing decision making (Lusk & Fater, 2014). The Institute of Medicine (2018) defined Patient Centred Care (PCC) "as providing care that is respectful of, and responsive to, individual preferences, needs and values, and ensuring that patient values guide all clinical decisions." The Patient Centred Care (PCC) has the potential to make care more tailored to the needs of the patients (Sanne, Jane, & Anna, 2019), when they are involved in decision making and their decisions are made final.

The principle of Patient-Centred Care (PCC) is dated back to the ancient Greek, which was in the particulars of each patient and it gained popularity in the 1970s (Tamiru, Mesfin, Temamen & Yeshitila 2017). Patient Centred Care is the practice of caring for the patients (and their families) in ways that are meaningful and valuable to the individual patient. Patients centered care involved listening to, informing and involving patients in their care. The Picker Institute identified eight dimensions of Patient Centred Care: respect for patients' preferences, values and expressed need, information, education and communication, coordination and interaction of care and services, emotional support, physical comfort, involvement of family and friends, continuity and transition and assess to care services. Patient Centred Care can only be practiced by nurses when they are well informed, the level of Nurses awareness about patient centred care will go a long way in determining their feelings, attitude and willingness to practice it.

The main objective was to determine the professional nurses' awareness and practice of Patient-Centered Care Approach to nursing care at Jericho Specialist Hospital, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. Specific Objectives were to: -

- determine the level of awareness of nurses working at Jericho Specialist Hospital to Patient-Centered Care approach
- assess the practice of Patient - Centered Care approach by the nurses working at Jericho Specialist Hospital

Research Questions

1. What is the level of awareness of nurses working at Jericho Specialist Hospital to Patient-Centered Care approach?
2. What is the level of practice of Patient-Centered Care approach by the nurses working at Jericho Specialist Hospital?

Research Hypothesis:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between nurses' awareness and practice of Patient-Centered Care approach.

Literature/ Theoretical Underpinning

Patient centred care involves knowledge of individual as a whole person, involving them and where appropriates their family and friends in helping to assess their own needs and plan their own care (Rollin, 2011). A trusting relationship is require for a nurse to be genuine with their patients, empathize with them i.e. understand patient's world from their own perspective, value them without judging them. Overtime, patient will develop a sense of congruence, where the self and the ideal self-meet. This process of self-actualization makes patient to gain confidence and self-esteem, making them open to new feelings and experiences, focusing on life as a process rather than a goal and valuing deep relationship with others (Rogers, 1959).

The implication of Roger's theory to nursing profession is that, Caring, Choice and Education are central to Patient Centred Care, which is also related to increased patient's satisfaction. However, this move from a dependent passive patient to an empowered partner in care requires a trusting relationship in which nurses do not react negatively to non-compliance. Instead, nurses should support them to express their fears and concerns, in order to develop a trusting relationship that will promote self - caring behaviour. These humanistic concepts of "respect for persons, individual right to self - determination, mutual respect, and understanding" underpinning patient centred care (McCormack et.al, 2011)

When interacting with the patients; they should be treated as an individual, cues should be taking from them regarding their interests, concerns and wishes. Nurses should try to see their situation as they understand it and do not dismiss their views or fears. Every care episode to develop a trusting relationship should be used, nurses must ensure needed knowledge is given to them and empower them to make decision. Patient should be included in care planning, process, focusing on communicating to understand and meet their views of their care needs. For patient centred care to be effectively practiced by clinical nurses, understanding of the concept is paramount, and must be well informed. Inadequate knowledge and unwillingness to practice it can negatively impact the practice.

Awareness of Nurses on Patient- Centered Care

Understanding what Patient Centered Care entails can serve as an eye opener and greatly influence nurses' view of the approach in nursing care. Without adequate knowledge of what Patient-Centered Care is all about, there may be difficulty in incorporating it into nursing care practice and thereby results in inadequacy in its implementation by the nurses. Draper and Tetley (2013) opined that the level of awareness of the nurses is a significant factor influencing practice of patient-centered care services. Professional nurses perceive Patient-Centered Care as an awareness of the importance of the patient's culture, involving the patient's family, incorporating values of love and respect, optimal communication in all facets of patient care and accountability to the patient (Sihaam & Portia, 2016). With Patient Centred Care, a patient relationship is created to facilitate trust and compliance to treatment. As nurses discharge their duties, Empathy, two-way communication, and eye-eye contact are crucial as it is the ability of the nurse to see beyond a patient's immediate problem. In a Patient Centred Care model, nurses should give opportunity to deliver what patients want, gain their trust and build rapport with them as this improves compliance with treatment, bringing about better health outcomes and it also improves patient's independence. For

example, strict visiting hours and visitors' restrictions are a thing of the past, patients are given the authority to identify who can visit and when (Rosewilliam, 2019).

In a study carried out by Gemmae, Carol-van Deusen, and Barbara (2018), Patient Centered Care as partnership between patients and nurses, some see it as sharing power and responsibilities involving learning from patients while to some, it required listening to the patient and having the patient as part of the team. One provider explained that Patient Centred Care meant allowing the patient to choose care plan, even if that meant going against recommendation. A Nursing Director (DNS) said that Patient Centred Care means providers need to accept patient's life choices, which is a change for both patients and providers. An integrative Medicine Manager characterized Patient Centred Care as not just a matter of relationship but one that could serve as a foundation for individualized care.

Practice of Patient Centered Care by Nurses

Nursing care is doing something to or for a patients or providing information to the patient with the intention of meeting needs, increasing self – ability, or alleviating impairments, thus, making patients become healthier (Petiprin, 2020). In Patient Centred Care, caring is central to nursing practice, and nurses' relationship with the patient are fundamental to that patient's experience of care. The patient's role is one of the partnership rather than a passive receiver of care. A person centred relationship promotes self-esteem (positive self-regard) and self-efficacy (a feeling of being able to achieve one's goals), choice and education (Ortiz, 2018).

Patient Centred Care is increasingly recognized as a key dimension of quality healthcare, but unfortunately, remains poorly implemented in practice (De Man, 2016). Patient Centred Care implementation has to do with involving the patient in their care which to some nurses view as given their responsibilities as a nurse to the patient thus makes them insignificant. Patient centred care approach have prevented errors and mismanagement of patient both at the nurses and physician ends. Maxson et al. (2012) found that involving the patient in nursing bed reports increases the patient satisfaction and improves safety in nursing practice such as reducing medication errors and improving communication with a physician. Licata, Aneja, and Kyper, et al (2013), found out that bedside round which included medical staff, nursing staff, patients and family members, improves communication between all participants in the round and increases the percentage of detected errors by 26%. Also, implementation of the Patient Centred Care approach during bedside reporting in the emergency department yielded similar outcomes of improvement in patient satisfaction scores and a significant reduction in errors associated with shift changes (Cronin-Waelde & Sbardella, 2013).

The Patient Centred Care approach focuses holistically on the patient as an individual, rather than their diagnosis or symptoms and ensures that their needs and choices are heard and respected (UK Essay, 2018). Nurses are expected to practice in a caring, knowledgeable, professional, courteous and non-judgmental manner, and the majority do this as a matter of principle, displaying unconditional positive regards for their patients at all times. Brink and Skott (2013), affirmed that some diagnosis lead to preconceptions about the individual receiving them, which subsequently negatively influence their care and treatment. For example, those requiring treatment for alcohol abuse or substance misuse may also experience a less empathetic experience in the care of nurses. They also stated that ethical considerations may influence the treatment of patients undergoing procedures to terminate

pregnancy and may negatively influence the extent to which the care received by the patient is truly Patient Centered Care.

Some nurses opined that giving patients a greater degree of autonomy over their care can lead to some discord as nurses may feel that their professional expertise is being disregarded and may be concerned that patients' informed opinions and decisions about their care may be detrimental to recovery or good health. However, if the patient is deemed to have capacity to make informed decisions about their care and treatment with all the facts at their disposal, nurses must accept this if good Patient -Centered Care is to be delivered (NHS Choices, 2014). In the event that the patient does not have the capacity to make informed decisions (e.g. patients suffering from more advanced forms of dementia), nurses may make assumptions regarding what is best for the patients, rather than respecting their choices and preferences (UK Essay, 2018). Nurses' role in implementation of the Patient Centred Care is most imperative as they stay 24 hours at the bedside of the patient. Ratings of quality of nursing care in hospitals by patients, had the most significant effect on the overall experience of care and services, even more than the experience of care provided by a physician or housekeeping services (Natan & Hotchman, 2017).

Factors enabling Patient Centred Care were a positive work environment for staff, nursing managers demonstrating exemplary professional leadership, continuous in-service education for staff and collaborative teamwork within the interdisciplinary team. Patient Centred Care approach is complex and these contribute to the difficulties in implementing it in practice and there are those who doubt its efficacy and feasibility (Natan & Hotchman, 2017). The era of evidenced- based nursing practice has brought about the necessity of Patient- Centered Care approach to nursing practice. Patients are at the core center of the healthcare, to gain their maximum cooperation and for them to experience satisfaction with the rendered treatment and nursing services, there is need for them to be involved in their care and treatment plan, to get a quality, efficient and effective nursing care and to achieve positive health outcome. Therefore, the study was focused on examining the awareness, and practice of Patient Centered Care in a selected government hospital.

Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was adopted using questionnaires to elicit response from respondents. A questionnaire used by Martinez and Muniz (2009) in their study conducted on Assessment of Patient Centred Care in Gerontology Services was adopted, and structured questionnaire developed by the researcher after literature review were used to answer the research questions to meet the research objectives. The study was carried out in a purposively selected hospital in Ibadan, Oyo-state of Nigeria, due to the large number of patients that are being attended to in the setting. The study population was all professional nurses working presently in the hospital. Purposive sampling was employed in the study. Total enumeration was used in the study meaning all nurses who were on duty as at the time of data collection were included in the study.

A structured questionnaire was used to explore their opinions as regard the nurses' awareness and practice of Patient Centered Care. The questionnaire contained three (3) sections.

SECTION A: This section contains items that were used to elicit information on demographic data, which comprises 9 questions.

SECTION B: contains 13 items on the awareness of nurses of Patient Centered Care approach in nursing care. The instrument used in this section was structured questionnaire, developed by the researcher after literature review. Questions were framed to meet the study's objectives and to answer research questions.

SECTION C: contains 12 items on the practice of patient centered care by the nurses at the selected hospitals. A questionnaire used by Martinez and Muniz (2009) in their study conducted on Assessment of PCC in Gerontology Services: A new tool for healthcare professionals was adopted to answer the research questions and to meet the research objectives

Participants were required to give response to all items. The questionnaire was constructed in English Language and it consisted of 34 items in 3 sections.

The instrument for data collection was subjected to face and content validity technique. The questionnaire was given to an expert in nursing management and practice and statistical analyst for critiquing, suggestions and amendments. Reliability is the degree to which an assessment tool produces stable and consistent results. A pilot study was carried out on small population 10% (21) of the sample size on nurses working at Jericho Nursing Home, Jericho, Ibadan, Oyo State (JNH). The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's alpha^a method, awareness of nurses to Patient Centered Care was 0.826 and practice of Patient Centered Care was 0.719.

The instrument was administered to the respondents on the day approved by the selected hospital authority for the exercise. In the selected hospital, the administration and collection of the instrument was done for three days. The data collected from the study was analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis at 0.05 level of significance. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the research and their consents were obtained before the administration of the questionnaires.

Results

Demographic information of the Nurses

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	20-30years	15	33.3
	31-40years	6	13.3
	41-50years	21	46.7
	51-60years	3	6.7
Gender	Male	5	11.1
	Female	40	88.9
Religion	Christianity	27	60.0
	Muslim	14	31.1
	Others	4	8.9
Marital Status	Married	23	51.1
	Single	19	42.2
	Widow	3	6.7
Designation	Senior Nurse	29	64.4
	Charge Nurse	16	35.6
Highest academic qualification	Diploma in nursing	14	31.1
	BSc Nursing Science	16	35.6

	MSc Nursing Science	9	20.0
	Others	6	13.3
Years of experience	1-10years	15	33.3
	11-20years	6	13.3
	21-30years	23	51.1
	31years and above	1	2.2
Ward/Unit	Medical Unit	13	28.9
	Surgical Unit	9	20.0
	Emergency Unit	14	31.1
	Pediatric Unit	6	13.3
	Gynecological Unit	1	2.2
	Operating Room	2	4.4
Tribe	Yoruba	40	88.9
	Hausa	1	2.2
	Igbo	4	8.9

The table 1 above indicated that majority of the respondents are between ages of 41-50years, 33.3% of the nurses that participated are between the ages of 20-30years, 13.3% are between the ages of 31-40years, 88.9% of the nurses are predominantly nurses, 11.1% are male, 60.1% of the respondents are Christian by faith, 31.1% of the nurses are Muslim while 8.9% represent other religion affiliation. 51.1% of the respondents are married, 42.2% are single while 6.7% are widow. More than 60% of the respondents are senior nurses while 35.6% are charge nurses. Majority of the nurses have a first degree in nursing science while 31.1% have a diploma nursing certificate while 20% of the respondents have a Master degree in nursing science while 13.3% have other academic qualification related to nursing science. 33.3% of the respondents have between 1-10years working experience, 51.1% have between 20-30years work experience, 13.3% had 11-20years work experience as a nurse and 2.2% had more than 31years working as a Nurse. 28.9% of the respondents are in the Surgical Unit, 20% of the nurses are in medical unit, 31.1% are in Emergency unit, and 13.3% are in Pediatric unit, 4.4% are in the operating room while 2.2% are in Gynecological Unit. 88.9% of the nurses are predominantly from the Yoruba tribe, 8.9% are from the Igbo tribe while 2.2% are from Hausa tribe.

Table 2 Awareness of Nurses toward Patient Centered Care

S/NO	ITEMS	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	PCC is the practice of caring for patients in the ways that are meaningful and valuable to the individual patients.	5(11.1%)	10(22.2%)	12(26.7%)	13(28.9%)	5(11.1%)
2	The origin of PCC can be traced to Florence Nightingale.	12(26.7%)	8(17.8%)	9(20%)	13(28.9%)	3(6.7%)
3	PCC involves listening to, informing and involving patients in their care.	4(8.9%)	2(4.4%)	12(26.7%)	23(51.1%)	4(8.9%)

4	PCC focus is not only on the illness but also on the whole-health wellness.	12(26.7%)	3(6.7%)	18(40%)	12(26.7%)	0(0%)
5	PCC is creating partnership between patients and nurses.	3(6.7%)	7(15.6%)	13(28.9%)	13(28.9%)	9(20%)
6	PCC means nurses need to accept patient's life and treatment choices.	12(26.7%)	3(6.7%)	10(22.2%)	17(37.8%)	3(6.7%)
7	PCC bring about better health outcomes and improves patient's independence.	3(6.7%)	16(35.6%)	10(22.2%)	8(17.8%)	8(17.8%)
8	PCC facilitates trust and compliances to treatments.	7(15.6%)	4(8.9%)	9(20%)	15(33.3%)	10(22.2%)
9	Empathy is the ability of the nurse to see beyond a patient's immediate problems.	2(4.4%)	14(31.1%)	0(0%)	16(35.6%)	13(28.9%)
10	PCC makes nurses support those patients who may not be able to directly communicate their needs and wants.	1(2.2%)	0(0%)	17(37.8%)	20(44.4%)	7(15.6%)
11	PCC requires nurses to understand individuals' differences during nursing care.	9(20%)	2(4.4%)	2(4.4%)	21(46.7%)	11(24.4%)
12	Patients often lose their independence and their dignity when they enter healthcare settings.	4(8.9%)	9(20%)	11(24.4%)	11(24.4%)	10(22.2%)
13	Goal of PCC is to empower patients to become active participants in their care.	12(26.7%)	3(6.7%)	12(26.7%)	12(26.7%)	6(13.3%)

Table 2 presented above indicated that majority of the respondents are aware that PCC is the practice of caring for patients in the ways that are meaningful and valuable to the individual patients, also most of the nurses aware that the origin of PCC can be traced to Florence Nightingale. Majority of the respondents 51.1% agreed that PCC involves listening to, informing and involving patients in their care, 40% of the respondents agreed that PCC focus is not only on the illness but also on the whole-health wellness, 28.9% of the respondents agreed that PCC is creating partnership between patients and nurses, 37.8% of the respondent strongly agreed that PCC means nurses need to accept patient's life and treatment choices, 35.6% of the respondents agreed that PCC bring about better health outcomes and improves patient's independence. 33.3% of the respondents agreed that PCC facilitates trust and compliances to treatments, 35.6% of the respondents agreed that Empathy is the ability of the nurse to see beyond a patient's immediate problems, 44.4% of the respondents agreed that PCC makes nurses support those patient who may not be able to directly communicate their needs and wants, 46.7% of the nurses agreed that PCC requires nurses to understand individuals differences during nursing care, 24.4% of the respondents disagreed that Patients often lose their independence and their dignity when they enter healthcare settings, 26.7% of the respondents agreed that the goal of PCC is to empower patients to become active participants in their care

Table 3: Practice of Patient-Centered Care

S/NO	Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
1,	In this centre, nurses recognize patients as people and not just as their illness or diseases.	1(2.2%)	13(28.9%)	17(37.8%)	8(17.8%)	6(13.3%)
2.	We have information about the life histories of the people in our care, we know their habits and interests and their likes and dislikes.	1(2.2%)	6(13.3%)	18(40%)	17(37.8%)	3(6.7%)
3.	Patients can make decisions about their care (for example when to get up or go to bed, when to bath or what cloths to wear).	8(17.8%)	10(22.2%)	3(6.7%)	19(42.2%)	5(11.1%)

4.	Patient's care and activities are decided bearing in mind their life history and observation of their wellbeing.	8(17.8%)	3(6.7%)	17(37.8%)	13(28.9%)	4(8.9%)
6.	We listen to and understand each patient's problems and concerns, always trying to put ourselves in their shoes.	16(35.6%)	4(8.9%)	5(11.1%)	16(35.6%)	4(8.9%)
7.	The staffs are flexible, we can change times and rules depending on the day-day needs of the people in our care.	3(6.7%)	6(13.3%)	18(40%)	15(33.3%)	3(6.7%)
9.	The patient's private matters are treated with utmost discretion and respect, even when they advanced cognitive impairment.	9(20%)	12(26.7%)	13(28.9%)	11(24.4%)	0(0%)
10.	The people in our care are can do their hobbies and spend time doing what they like.	15(33.3%)	6(13.3%)	12(26.7%)	9(20%)	3(6.7%)
11.	The wards reflect the life and personality of those admitted in them.	16(35.6%)	6(13.3%)	6(13.3%)	12(26.7%)	5(11.1%)
12.	The hospital encourages religious bodies and non-governmental organizations to come and participate in activities.	20(44.4%)	10(22.2%)	10(22%)	0(0%)	5(11.1%)

Table 3 represented above indicated that majority of the nurses were undecided that centre nurses' recognizes patients as people and not just as their illness or diseases, also 40% of the nurses were also undecided about information about the life histories of the people in our care, we know their habits and interests and their likes and dislikes. 42.2% of the nurses agreed that Patients can make decisions about their care (for example when to get up or go to bed, when to bath or what cloths to wear. Majority of the nurses were undecided that Patient's care and activities are decided bearing in mind their life history and observation of their wellbeing while most of the nurses agreed that patient are treated with respect. Additionally, majority of the respondents 35.6% of the nurses listen to and understand each patient's problems and concerns, always trying to put ourselves in their shoes. 40% of the respondents that staffs are flexible, we can change times and rules depending on the day-day needs of the people in our care. Most of the nurses were agree they get personalized care is given, majority of the respondents agreed that patient's private matters are treated with utmost discretion and respect, even when they advanced cognitive impairment. Also, majority of the nurses 33.3% disagree people in our care are can do their hobbies and spend time doing what they like. 44.4% disagreed that hospital encourages religious bodies and non-governmental organizations to come and participate in activities. Most of the nurses agreed that people in care are encouraged to get out of bed to exercise that as they cannot do it alone, someone is sought to accompany them.

Table 4: Level of Awareness towards Patient Centered Care

Level of awareness	Frequency	Percentage
High	29	64.4
Fair	9	20.0
Poor	7	15.6
Total	45	100.0

Table presented above indicated that majority of the nurses had 64.4% high level of awareness about patient centered care in the hospital, 20% are aware, 15.6% had poor level of awareness. This implies that majority the nurses aware of the use of patient centeredness when providing care and support for patients in the hospital.

Table 5: Level of Practice towards Patient Centered Care

Level of Practice	Frequency	Percentage
Good	20	44.4
Moderate	17	37.8
Poor	8	17.8
Total	45	100.0

Table 5 above revealed that 44% of the nurses have good level of practice of patients centered care services in the hospital, 37.8% had moderate level of practice and 17.8% had poor level of Patient Centered Care services in the hospital. The implication is that majority have good level of consistency in terms of practice of Patient Centered Care Services.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between nurses' awareness and practice of patient-centered care approach.

Table 6: Showing relationship between nurses' awareness and practice of patient-centered care approach.

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Awareness of Patient-centred approach	61.7556	5.3773	45	.861	.000	Sig.
Practice of Patient-centred approach	60.0667	6.3511				

Table 6 above showed that there was a positive significant relationship between nurses' awareness and practice of patient-centered care approach ($r = .861$, $N = 260$, $p < .05$). It could be deduced from the result above that there was a significant relationship between nurses' awareness and practice of patient-centered care approach. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of findings

The result of research question one showed that 64.4% of the nurses have high level of awareness about patient centered care in the hospital. The result corroborates the findings of Gemmae, Carol-van Deusen, and Barbara (2018), on a study on Patient Centered Care as partnership between patients and nurses, some see it as sharing power and responsibilities involving learning from patients while to some, it required listening to the patient and having the patient as part of the team. One provider explained that Patient Centred Care meant allowing the patient to choose care plan, even if that meant going against recommendation. A Nursing Director (DNS) said that Patient Centred Care means providers need to accept patient's life choices, which is a change for both patients and providers. Tamiru, Mesfin, Temamen and Yeshitila (2017) that patient centered care is very important for nurses most especially in teaching and research hospitals. Similar study was reported by Neoteryx (2019) that understanding the principle of patient centered care have significant impact on health outcomes of patients presented in the hospital, additionally, Better Health Channel (2018), also affirmed that patient centered care is about treating a person receiving healthcare with dignity and respect, involving them in all decisions about their health. It is an approach that linked a person to healthcare rights. Patients are put at the center of their healthcare.

Result of research question two indicated that 44% of the nurses have good level of practice of patients centered care services in the hospital, 37.8% had moderate level of

practice and 17.8% had poor level of practice of patient centered care services in the hospital. The result is consistent with that of De Man (2016) that increased practice of patient centered care has major benefit to patients' health outcome including improved quality healthcare, but unfortunately, remains poorly implemented in practice.

The result of hypothesis one indicated that there was a significant relationship between nurses' awareness and practice of patient-centered care approach. The result is consistent with that of Draper and Tetley (2013) that level of awareness of the nurses is a significant factor influencing practice of patient-centered care services.

Implication to Research and Practice

The era of problem centred care is obsolete, evidenced-based practice have ushered in Patient Centred Care. So, it is imperative for every nurse to be aware and employ this approach into their practice. Considering its impact on nursing practice; it create trusting relationship between nurses and patients thereby reduce the burden of care on the nurses, and bring about effective, efficient, adequate and satisfactory nursing care. It will also improve health outcome of the patient; involving patient in their care plan will bring out the best in them, allay their fear and anxiety and as well aid quick recovery thereby reduces hospital's stay and treatment cost.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Patient Centred Care approach in patients' care is critical as it is a main determinant of care quality; it is about treating patients in a way they want to be treated, as partnering with patient to elicit and achieve their goals of care is the right thing to do. The awareness of nurses on Patient Centred Care was good which means nurses were very much aware of Patient Centred Care approach, while practice was below average, which showed that nurses' awareness of Patient Centred Care does influence their practice of Patient Centred Care. This indicates that there is need for nurse administrator to ensure utilization of Patient Centred Care approach in their facility for effective, efficient and quality healthcare delivery to improve patients' health outcome and thereby produce nurses' satisfaction and joy.

Future Research

This study assessed the awareness and practice of Patient Centred Care in a selected government hospital in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. In view of this, further research is to be carried out to:

- (i) examine the effects of Patient Centred care approach on health outcome of the patients
- (ii) investigate interventions impacts on patient centred care approach on nursing practice.

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